

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENT LITERACY BASED ON THE PISA INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT PROGRAM'S CONCEPT 'LEARNING IN A DIGITAL WORLD'

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14251159>

Abstract. *This article examines the problems and their solutions within the framework of the PISA International assessment program on the transformation of digital technologies, changing the ways students learn in a digital environment, and developing a system for evaluating the quality of education.*

Keywords: *PISA International Assessment Program, digital technologies, digital competence, 4 assessment levels: recovery in memory and imagination, skills and understanding, strategic thinking, deep thinking.*

Introduction.

The digitalization efforts in our country are being carried out at a rapid pace, particularly in the field of education, as part of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 28, 2020, "Measures for the widespread implementation of digital economy and e-government" (PD-4699), and the Resolution dated October 5, 2020, "On approving the strategy of 'Digital Uzbekistan 2030' and measures for its implementation" (PR-6079). This includes the wide integration of digital technologies at all levels of the education system, improving the education infrastructure, promoting the development of digital education in the country, and implementing programs for the integration of digital technologies into the education system. In the rapidly evolving transformation era, characterized by deepening technology, digitalization, and globalization processes, the education system demands accelerated socio-economic development. In economically developed countries, the PISA (Programme for International Student Assessment), an international evaluation program assessing student achievements in education, is considered a key criterion in improving the quality of education. Additionally, adapting to the new digital world in human life and lifestyle, receiving education and training in a digital environment according to the PISA program, developing critical thinking for internet information, making rational decisions, solving real-life problems, and wisely using digital technologies emphasize the importance of digital competence and media literacy. The transformation of education through digital technologies, in line with the PISA international assessment program, is rapidly changing the methods of learning in the digital environment, as well as the trends in the development of the education quality assessment system.

Literature Review. Foreign scholars such as In Y. Rosen [4], D. S. Hirschberg [3], R. J. Adams, M. L. Wu, N. Teig, and others [5] have conducted research on the problems and solutions of using digital technologies in the PISA international assessment program, addressing the issues of developing digital competence in education.

Research Methodology. The development of digital competence and media literacy among students in the modern digital world is of great social and pedagogical importance. Let's

examine the main concepts and aspects of this issue. The digital world is formed in connection with technological, virtual, and global worlds and develops within the scope of interaction with the real world. According to the PISA international assessment program, scientific learning through computers and learning in a digital education environment require significant knowledge, skills, and competencies. Digital competence primarily encompasses knowledge, skills, and competencies.

Analysis and Results. In this process, scientific learning through computers, according to the PISA assessment program, involves not only the knowledge, skills, and competencies required for reading, text comprehension, and natural-scientific and mathematical literacy in a digital learning environment but also the new ideas, thoughts, innovative approaches, and solutions that can be derived from them. Therefore, it is considered appropriate to give a special place to digital competence in the classification of competencies. The PISA tasks are developed by internationally experienced experts, and creating similar tasks requires systematic and specialized knowledge. Tasks that do not adhere to the requirements of PISA can confuse students rather than help them. For this reason, in the process of preparing students for the PISA exams, it is more appropriate to focus not on solving specific PISA tasks but on enhancing the overall preparation level of students for solving such tasks and similar ones.

Regarding the modern requirements placed on the student's personality in the development of digital competence, the following can be noted:

Searching for the causes of events, finding unknown relationships in given quantities, approaching identified problems in new ways, applying the laws of specific sciences in non-traditional situations;

Solving non-standard problems, including those far removed from the field of knowledge being studied;

The ability to identify the main contradictions in the area of study and the ability to pose new issues and problems.

In organizing a digital learning environment in educational institutions, the following should be emphasized:

The development of self-regulated digital learning stages in education;

The development of digital competence through the formation of abilities to work in a digital environment;

Organizing pedagogy focused on digital and media literacy;

The development of digital competencies for both teachers and students.

In the PISA international assessment program's concept "Learning in a Digital World", student literacy is assessed in four levels: recall and reconstruction, skill and understanding, strategic thinking and deep thinking.

Level 1: The task requires recalling, identifying, and selecting learned knowledge. Key words: identify, recall, use, measure, describe. Problems are solved using learned principles.

Level 2: Tasks may be presented with the help of graphs, tables, and diagrams. Key words: classify, organize, evaluate, conduct observations, gather and show data, and compare data. Conclusions are drawn through comparison and analysis.

Level 3: This level requires reasoning and planning. Answers should be varied and well-supported. It includes presenting evidence, developing logical hypotheses, explaining events, and providing decisions used to solve complex problems.

Level 4: Tasks and problems are solved using information from various sources. Answers should be varied and well-supported. Data is compared, analyzed, and synthesized to draw conclusions.

In shaping and developing the digital competence of secondary school students, using the above-mentioned concept of digital competence and integrating it into relevant subject topics will help improve the levels of mastering these topics. Ensuring that students master subject topics deeply and become active participants and performers, rather than passive observers, is crucial in this process. Students must understand the role of mathematics in the world they live in and be able to justify mathematical processes correctly and thoroughly. The primary goal of this section is to ensure that individuals can use mathematics creatively, curiously, and thoughtfully to meet current and future needs for mathematical knowledge. The term "literacy" in this section is used to emphasize that the goal is not simply to determine the extent to which students master the knowledge typically given in the school curriculum. The focus is on the ability to apply different methods of thinking and making intuitive decisions in various real-life situations using mathematical knowledge. However, the knowledge and skills provided in the school curriculum may be necessary when answering such questions. In these assessments, mathematical situations related to different areas of life (such as medicine, housing, sports, etc.) are usually proposed.

In the digital world, the methodological processes aimed at prioritizing the effectiveness preferences of scientific learning with computers and learning in a digital environment are directed at developing independent creative thinking, organizational skills, practical experience, and metacognitive, cognitive, heuristic, motivational, and affective self-regulated learning stages.

Conclusion and Recommendations. In conclusion, it is necessary to take a comprehensive and systematic approach to developing the concept "Learning in a Digital World" in students. This approach should include forming technical skills in working with modern media technologies, as well as developing critical thinking, and the ability to analyze and evaluate information.

Secondly, it confirms the importance of engaging students in activities from the early years of the educational process. This not only helps in developing technical skills but also lays a solid foundation for further development of the ability to independently assess and select information in the digital space.

Analysis of PISA Data. The analysis of PISA data shows that students with higher literacy levels successfully perform tasks related to evaluating and analyzing digital information. Therefore, developing teaching methods aimed at fostering these competencies and integrating them into practice appears to be a crucial step in improving the quality of education and preparing students for the modern digital environment.

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